

Voluntary Reporting of Corporate Governance Information in Annual Reports: An Empirical Study of an Asian Country

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Abstract

The high-profile corporate governance (CG) failure scams (like the Stock Market scam, the UTI scam, Ketan Parikh scam, Satyam scam, etc.), which was severely criticized by the shareholders, called for a need to make CG in India transparent as it greatly affects the development of the country. The reporting of CG information is a fundamental theme of the 'modern' corporate-regulatory system, which encompasses providing 'governance' information to the public in a variety of ways. Reporting theory assumes the wide availability of information to users, increasing the level of corporate transparency and reducing information asymmetry common to the business environment.

This study explores the voluntary CG Reporting practices of 50 corporations, over and above the mandatory requirements of Clause 49 of the Listing Agreement. In order to study the voluntary CG Reporting practices, a "content analysis" was done, and finally, a "CG Reporting" Index was prepared. We have primarily used 'secondary' sources of information, both from the 'Report on CG' and the 'Annual Reports' for the financial year 2003-04 and 2004-05. As a part of voluntary CG reporting, a total of 40 items have been selected from the CG section of the Annual Reports and proxy forms. In order to provide a comparison 'across' industries, corporations have been selected from four industries, viz., software, textiles, sugar and paper. Appropriate statistical tools and techniques have been applied for the analysis. It has been observed that "corporations are following less than 50 percent of the items of CG Reporting Index. Moreover, there is no significant difference among the reporting scores across the four industries."

Key words: Voluntary, corporate governance, reporting, annual report, empirical study, clause 49, listing agreement, CG reporting index, Asian Country.

1. Introduction

Corporate governance (henceforth, 'CG') involves a set of relationships between a corporation's management, its board, its shareholders and other stakeholders. It also provides a principled process and structure through which the objectives of the corporation, the means of attaining the objectives, and systems of monitoring performance are set. Indeed, CG is a set of accepted principles by management of the inalienable rights of the shareholders as a 'true-owner' of the corporation, and of their own role as 'trustees' on behalf of the shareholders. The key aspects of 'good' CG include transparency of corporate structures and operations, the accountability of managers and the boards to shareholders; and corporate responsibility towards stakeholders. According to Bhasin (2016), "While CG essentially lays down the framework for creating the long-term trust between companies and the external providers of capital, it would be wrong to think that the importance of CG lies solely in better access of finance. Companies around the world are realizing that better CG adds considerable value to their operational performance by: (a) improving strategic thinking at the top by inducting independent directors, who bring a wealth of experience and a host of new ideas, (b) rationalizing the management and monitoring of risk that a firm faces globally, and (c) limiting the liability of top management and directors, by carefully articulating the decision making process."

"During the 1990s, a number of 'high-profile' corporate scandals in the USA and also elsewhere in the world, triggered an in-depth reflection on the regulatory role of the government in protecting the interests of shareholders," (Bhasin, 2016a). Thus, to redress the problem of corporate 'misconduct,' ensuring 'sound' CG is believed to be essential to maintaining investors' confidence and good performance. In view of the growing number of scandals and the subsequent wide-spread public and media interest in CG, a plethora of governance 'norms' and 'standards' have sprouted all around the globe (Patelli and Prencipe, 2007; Azlan et al., 2011). For instance, the Sarbanes-Oxley legislation in the USA, the Cadbury Committee

recommendations for the European Union (EU) corporations, and the OECD principles of CG, are perhaps the 'best-known' among these. The Cadbury Committee (1992) advocated first of all reporting (or disclosure) as "a mechanism for accountability, emphasizing the need to raise reporting standards in order to ward-off the threat of regulation." Similarly, the Hampel Committee (1998) regulated reporting as "the most important element of accountability and in introducing a new code and set of principles stated that their objective was not to prescribe corporate behaviour in detail but to secure sufficient reporting so that investors and others can assess corporations performance and governance practice and respond in an informed way."

Information is the foundation on which traders form their beliefs about a company and ultimately their investment decisions. In empirical settings, information often arrives in the form of both statutory and voluntary reporting by companies. However, a detailed and well-structured system of CG Reporting in the Annual Reports of corporations enables investors to understand, and obtain accurate and reliable information about the corporations in order to make 'better' investment decisions (Eng and Mak, 2003). Since managers' have significant discretion over reporting, several researchers has extensively studied the relation between reporting and stock trading via the market price determination system. According to Forte et al., (2016), "Reporting theory assumes the wide availability of information to users, increasing the level of corporate transparency and reducing information asymmetry common to the business environment." As Bhasin (2015) pointed out, "Reporting of information enables the shareholders' to evaluate the management's performance by observing, how efficiently the management is utilizing the corporation's resources in the interest of the principal. Successful business communication has five characteristics: simplicity, brevity, clarity, relevance and a human touch." One of the mechanisms that governance codes emphasized on is transparency and reporting. There is transparency and reporting when a company provides timely, adequate and reliable picture of its condition and operation as well as financial and economic performance in terms of quality and content through its financial statements, annual reports and performance evaluations. This mechanism enables shareholders, creditors and directors to monitor management effectively (Sharif and Lai, 2015). In fact, effective reporting will communicate your approach to CG in a way that readers can easily understand. Recently, the UNCTAD (2016) pointed out, "Corporate reporting (or disclosure) can play a key role in attaining the sustainable development goals (SDGs) as high quality and internationally comparable reporting contributes to financial stability, promotes 'good' governance, as well as socially and environmentally responsible practices—which are key to sustainable development. Being a principal source of information on companies' performance, it can also serve as an important part of the SDGs monitoring and review mechanism."

Recently, Bhasin reported (2016b), "Historically, private and public listed companies in India have reported/disclosed only as much information as is mandatory (or statutory). The justification—that the provision of additional information will be of greater interest to competitors rather than investors—has often been repeated by companies. But increasing regulatory activism and international institutional investors are demanding additional reporting from the India's 9,000-plus listed companies, in the interest of improving CG and removing information 'asymmetries' in the capital markets." Last year, the Securities and Exchange Board of India (henceforth, SEBI) introduced an amended clause 49 in the equity listing agreement that demands board level oversight for "reporting and communications", while acknowledging weak enforcement of mandatory reporting standards. In view of the current economic downturn, CG and reporting about governance may become a more pressing issue for the listed corporations, particularly if it relates to going-concern reporting, risk management, internal controls, board balance, and directors' remuneration (Nowland, 2008). According to Bhasin, 2010), "It should be noted that reporting of information by a corporation is like a "double-edge sword" in the management hands. Reporting about the firm's human resources, risk, and the like, are likely to be effective in reducing information 'asymmetries' and mitigating their need for price protection. On the other hand, reporting about the marketing strategies, R&D, technology, etc., might jeopardize the firm's 'competitive' advantage." Surprisingly, corporations are reluctant to report/discard the relevant information, which could tarnish their image," (Bhasin, 2011).

Accountability, transparency, fairness and reporting are the four “pillars” of the modern corporate regulatory system, and involve the provision of information by corporations to the ‘public’ in a variety of ways (Bhasin, 2015). For example, reporting can be viewed from two perspectives: corporate reporting and financial accounting reporting. Therefore, information and its “true-and-fair” reporting are the areas where corporation law and accounting regulations join hands together. It is a key objective of accounting rules, in general, to ensure that users’ have sufficient, reliable and timely availability of information in order to participate in the market, on an informed basis (Dragomir et al., 2009). According to the UNCTAD (2006) ‘Guidance on Good Practices in Corporate Governance Reporting,’ “All material issues relating to CG of the enterprise should be reported in a timely fashion. The reporting should be clear, concise, precise, and governed by the substance over form principle.” However, reporting requirements can sometime provide a more ‘efficient’ regulatory tool, than ‘substantive’ regulation, through more or less detailed rules. Substantive law, in fact, deals with rights and duties that are not matters purely of practice and procedure. Such reporting, however, creates a ‘lighter’ regulatory environment and allows for greater flexibility and adaptability. To sum up, reporting by a corporation is the ‘foundation’ of any structure of ‘good’ CG (Bhasin, 2015a).

‘Good’ CG standards are essential for the integrity of corporations, financial institutions and markets and have a bearing on the growth and stability of the economy. Over the past decade and a half, India has made significant strides in the areas of CG reforms, which have improved public trust in the market. These reforms have been well received by the investors, including the foreign institutional investors (FIIs). In this context, Bhasin (2016c) recently remarked as: “A compelling evidence of the improving standards comes from the growing interest of FIIs in the Indian market; gross FII portfolio investment has risen from USD 2.7 billion in FY 1996 to USD 203.2 billion in FY 2014. Governance reforms and globalization of the capital markets have been mutually reinforcing. While continuing governance reforms have led to rising foreign investment, globalization of the capital markets has provided an impetus toward a more stringent CG regime by the Indian industry itself.” To market their securities to foreign investors, Indian companies making public offerings in India were persuaded to comply with CG norms that investors in the developed world were familiar with. As Bhasin (2015) observed, “Indian companies listing abroad to raise capital were subject to stiff CG requirements applicable to listing on those Exchanges. They also adhered to the norms and practices of CG applicable to markets where they listed their securities. It must however be recognized that such practices have remained largely confined to only some large companies and have not percolated to majority of Indian companies.”

The CG guidelines and codes have evolved over a period in India by SEBI and various Committees’ setup by the Parliament to come up with the guidelines on CG to Indian Companies. The issue of understanding and application of CG in ‘letter and spirit’ is very important for any organization to be successful and competitive in the long run (Jha and Mehra, 2015). Well, over a hundred different codes and norms have been identified in recent surveys and their number is steadily increasing. As Jamie Allen (2008) stated that “most of the countries/markets in the Asian region had taken the initiative long-back in 1990s by formulating and implementing an official code of CG.” Fortunately, India has been no exception to this rule. A recent study titled “CG Watch 2014: Corporate Governance in Asia” puts India in the 7th position among the Asian countries, in terms of overall CG score. Although India’s overall CG Watch market score has increased from 51 in 2012 to 54 in 2014, its overall ranking has remained the same. The sharp increase in scores of two categories, such as, ‘CG Rules and Practices’ and ‘CG Culture’ mainly contributed to the increase in overall market score, as shown in **Table 1**.

Table 1: Corporate Governance Quality: Market Category Scores in percent

Rank	Country	Total	CG Rules & Practices	Enforcement	Political and Regulatory	IGAAP	CG Culture
1	Hong Kong	65	61	71	69	72	51
1	Singapore	64	63	56	64	85	54
3	Japan	60	48	62	61	72	55
4	Thailand	58	62	51	48	80	50
4	Malaysia	58	55	47	59	85	43
5	Taiwan	56	48	47	63	75	47
7	India	54	57	46	58	57	51
8	Korea	49	46	46	45	72	34
9	China	45	42	40	44	67	34
10	Philippines	40	40	18	42	65	33
10	Indonesia	39	34	24	44	62	32

(Source: CG Watch 2014—Corporate Governance in Asia, CLSA Asia-Pacific Markets)

Globally, there is both increased realization and acceptability that good CG is a means to create a business environment of trust, transparency and accountability in order to support investment, financial stability and sustainable economic growth. In the global and highly interconnected world of business and finance, where money and CG operations constantly cross borders, creating trust is something that we need to do together (Deloitte, 2015). The passing of the long-awaited Companies Act, 2013 is probably the single most important development in India's history of corporate legislation, next only to the monumental Companies Act 1956 which it replaces. Bhasin (2013c) remarked, "While significant improvements have been effected in required standards of CG, there is also some concern regarding overly increasing compliance and regulatory costs and efforts for companies as well as their independent directors." Among the major provisions of the Act are those of restraining voting rights of interested shareholders on related party transactions, recognition of board accountability to stakeholders besides shareholders, and extension of several good governance requirements to relatively large unlisted corporations (Balasubramanian, 2014).

2. Corporate Governance: Tracking International Developments

The Companies Act, 2013 has raised the bar for the Boards in India. Here, Bhasin (2013a, b) summed up the scenario as: "The new concepts introduced in the Act, such like—women directors on the Boards to bring in gender diversity, enhanced reporting norms, small shareholder director, performance evaluation of Boards and directors, mandating corporate social responsibility, introducing the possibility of class actions; including internal financial controls and risk management as a part of oversight of the Boards and enhancing the role of the Independent Directors—aim at enhancing the protection for minority shareholders, provide for investor protection and activism, a better framework for insolvency regulation and thus strengthen the foundations of good governance in Indian companies."

Key Global Trends in Corporate Governance and Indian Regulatory Initiatives

International Trends	Corporate Governance Requirements in India
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Asia: Independent Directors are a requirement for listed companies in all Asian economies, where most require at least 1/3rd of the Board to be independent. The 2012 Singapore CG Code recommends a majority of Independent Directors when the chairman of the Board is not independent. • US: The Council of Institutional Investors (CII), Corporate Governance Policies state that at least 2/3rd of the directors should be independent. • Europe: European commission urges member states to have sufficient number of independent non-executive or supervisory directors on Board. • G20/OECD: The latest principles encourage the prominent role of independent Board members. It states that, it is a good practice where remuneration policy and contracts for Board members and key executives is handled by a special committee of the Board comprising either wholly or a majority of Independent Directors. 	<p>Independent Directors</p> <p>Board to have specific proportion of Independent Directors</p>
<p>Although, there is no specific law to enforce number of women directors on the Board, following countries have taken steps to maintain the ratio of female</p>	<p>Woman Director</p>

<p>Board representation (source: www.cfainstitute.org):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Japan: In early 2014, Japanese Prime Minister announced the goal of increasing the percentage of women in executive positions at Japanese companies to 30% by 2020. • UK: UK businesses had voluntary targets first set in 2011 i.e. to have 25% women on FTSE100 (The Financial Times Stock Exchange) Boards by 2015. • Canada: At the Federal level, two bills are currently being tabled which will impose a 40% quota for female Board members of public companies and other regulated entities such as banks and insurance companies. • Brazil: A bill pending in the Brazilian Senate would impose a 40% female quota on the Boards of state-owned enterprises by 2022. • France: French parliament adopted a bill that requires public companies making at least 50 million euros in turnover and employing more than 500 workers to have 40% female Board representation by 2017. • Europe: The European Commission has proposed legislation that would require nonexecutive directors to be 40% women by 2020, up from 16.6% in 2013. • Germany: In November 2013, Germany's Christian Democrats and Social Democrats agreed on a gender quota on supervisory Boards where, issuers would be required to have women comprise 30% of nonexecutive directors by 2016. The planned legislation would require firms that don't meet the 30% mark to leave those seats vacant. <p>The latest G20/OECD principles encourages measures, such as voluntary targets, reporting requirements, Boardroom quotas, and private initiatives that enhance gender diversity on Boards and in senior management.</p>	<p>Requirement of at least 1 woman director on the Board for listed companies and public companies</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Asia: Committees of Boards, such as audit, remuneration and Board nomination are required in all Asian economies except Vietnam. In China, the Audit Committee is to be composed of Independent Directors only. • Europe: European Commission in 2005 recommended that companies set up committees on the (supervisory) Board to deal with nomination, remuneration and audit issues. • US: The Nominating and Corporate Governance Committee is one of the three standing committees, along with Audit Committee and Compensation Committee, required by NYSE, to be composed entirely of Independent Directors. <p>G20/ OECD principles encourages formulation of Nomination Committee to ensure proper compliance with established nomination procedures and to facilitate and co-ordinate the search for a balanced and qualified Board.</p>	<p>Formulation of various Committees</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Audit Committee, • Advisory Committee, • Nomination and Remuneration Committee, • Stakeholder Relationship Committee
<p>US: The U.S. National Association of Corporate Directors (NACD) recommends that the Governance Committee should be responsible for ensuring that a process exists for the Board to routinely assess its own performance, the performance of its Committees, as well as, individual directors to conduct self-assessment.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Europe: The Commission of the European Communities in 2009 recommended that director's remuneration should be based on performance. Variable components of remuneration should be linked to predetermined and measurable performance criteria, including criteria of a non-financial nature. The UK Corporate Governance Code recommends evaluation of the Board of FTSE 350 companies to be externally facilitated at least every three years (on a comply-or-explain basis) • Brazil: IBGC Code of Best Practices (Brazilian Institute of Corporate Governance) recommends: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> —A formal evaluation process of the performance of the Board, of individual directors and of the CEO —The process to be conducted by the Chair —Participation of the outsider to make the process more effective —Evaluation system adapted to each organization —Reporting of the process of evaluation to the shareholders • Mexico: Mexican Corporate Governance code recommends performance evaluation of the Board and its members as fiduciary duties. <p>The revised G20/ OECD principles on corporate governance recommends that Boards should regularly carry out evaluations to appraise their performance and assess whether they possess the right mix of background and competences.</p>	<p>Performance Evaluations of the Board, Committees and Directors</p> <p>Independent Director's and Committee's performance evaluation by the Board is mandatory</p>

Brazil: IBGC CG Code states that directors should ensure that the RPTs are conducted according to the market practices in terms of deadlines and rates and are clearly reflected in the organization reports. There is a prohibition on the loans in favor of the controlling partner and the administrators. The operations should be based on the independent appraisal reports and information endorsed by third parties. Loans between related parties should be avoided.

G20/ OECD: RPTs should be approved and conducted in a manner that ensures proper management of conflict of interest and protects the interest of the company and its shareholders. Conflicts of interest inherent RPTs should be addressed through proper monitoring and reporting.

In most jurisdictions, great emphasis is placed on the Board approval, often with prominent role for independent Board members or requirements for the Board to justify the interest of transaction for the company. Shareholders are also given a say in approving certain transactions, excluding the interested shareholders.

Related Party Transactions (RPTs)

- Formulation of RPT policy
- Prior Board Resolution at a meeting required for specified transactions with related parties.
- Exemption for transactions in ordinary course of business and an arm's length basis
- Prior approval of Audit Committee required for all RPTs

Canada: In 2013, Canada launches SVX, the Social Venture Exchange, one of the first social stock exchanges. It self-describes as a private investment platform made to connect impact ventures funds and Investors'.

Brazil: In 2012, Bovespa releases 'comply or explain' recommendations for all listed companies, encouraging them to state whether they publish a regular sustainability report and where it is available, or explain why not.

Australia: In 2014, The Australian Securities Exchange (ASX) updated their non-financial reporting requirements, now requiring companies to disclose if they have material exposure to 'environmental and social sustainability risks' and how they plan to manage and mitigate this risk. In 2010 Companies listed on ASX must disclose if they have developed a code of conduct on environmental risks and controls.

China: In 2008, China's State-owned Assets Supervision and Administration Commission (SASAC) releases a directive strongly encouraging state-owned enterprises to follow sound CSR practices and report on CSR activities. While this directive is not binding, SASAC holds a lot of influence in the business community, and such a directive demonstrates serious commitment to corporate social responsibility.

UK: In 2013, The Financial Reporting Council (FRC) in the UK announces that it is finalizing guidance on companies' reportings on environmental, social, and diversity issues. The new strategic report requires companies to provide a complete picture of their business activity, including social effects, calling into question what is material in business reporting.

Germany: In 2011, The German Council for Sustainable Development (GCSD) develops a German Sustainability Code. It includes 20 criteria and 27 GRI Performance Indicators that describe what should be taken into account in sustainability and reporting analysis.

France: In 2012, The Grenelle II Act is passed, requiring companies to include ESG (Environmental, Social and Governance) information in their annual report. Large companies are to comply in their 2012 reports, and smaller companies (defined as having fewer than 500 employees and total assets or net annual sales of €100 million) are to comply by 2014.

Corporate Social Responsibility

- **CSR Committee:** >= 3 directors, 1 Independent Director (ID)
- **CSR Policy:** To formulate the policy by CSR Committee
- **CSR Projects:** Schedule VII of The Companies Act, 2013 prescribes the CSR projects
- **CSR Report:** Disclose and report CSR policy and activities undertaken by the Company
- **CSR spend:** At least 2% of the average net profit of the Company in the immediately 3 preceding years

(Source: European Corporate Governance Institute: <http://www.ecgi.org/codes>)

3. Types of CG Reporting Required in India

A country's government environment—especially legal and market infrastructure—highly affect the companies' rate of reporting which then increases profitability. Good legislation and a market environment that is free from corruption are essential for corporate governance reporting to be efficient. According to Bhasin (2006, 2008), "Corporate financial reporting in the Annual Reports is a system of communication between the management and the user-groups of the financial statements, in order to report the results of the

business activities of a corporate enterprise. It seeks to demonstrate the credibility, accountability and reliability of its reporting.” In the Indian context, corporate financial reporting has two aspects, viz., statutory (mandatory) and non-statutory (voluntary) reporting.

(a) Statutory Reporting: In India, both the Company Act and the Securities and Exchange Rules, laid down by the SEBI, under Clause 49 of Listing Rules. The Company Act provides the basic requirements for reporting and reporting applicable to all corporations (or companies) incorporated in India. As Bhasin (2009) concludes, “The Act requires corporations to prepare financial statements in order to reflect a “true-and-fair” view of the state of affairs. The Act has made it compulsory for all corporations to maintain certain sets of books of account for recording the financial transactions, and to publish its annual statements in the prescribed form, from time to time. The Securities Exchange Board of India (SEBI), another regulatory body, requires all the ‘listed’ corporations to comply with accounting standards promulgated by the Institute of Chartered Accountants of India (ICAI), in addition to, its own reporting provisions. Reporting rules of SEBI are, in fact, restricted only to corporations listed on the all the stock exchanges within India. “It is often alleged that corporation Annual Reports do not comply with the reporting requirements stipulated by the regulatory agencies, resulting in poor reporting compliance by the listed corporations,” (Bhasin, 2010).

(b) Non-Statutory (Voluntary) Reporting: Non-statutory reporting is also “at par in importance with the statutory reporting to give the complete idea of the corporations business and future prospects,” (Bhasin, 2010a). Voluntary reporting items may be classified into historical, current and predictive items, depending on the past, present or envisaged performance of the corporation. However, it is ‘discretionary’ to provide non-statutory information, purely on a voluntary basis, in the Annual Reports. It depends on the corporation’s policy to disclose it. Recently, Bhasin (2016) has emphasized, “Of late, majority of the Indian corporations have been increasingly disclosing non-statutory information, which is not required as per the regulations. To raise awareness regarding their future prospects, corporations give extra information to their investors, creditors, customers and public at large. In modern times, many well-known and prosperous corporations have also come out with new and innovative patterns of presentation and furnish non-statutory information, such as, social responsibility and environmental reporting, value added statement, human resource accounting, inflation accounting, economic value added, brand valuation and intellectual capital statement etc.”

4. The Determinants of and Incentives for Voluntary Reporting of Information by Companies

Studies have demonstrated that ‘VCGR’ is the result of multiple factors interacting amongst each other. These factors include: regulatory oversight, market forces, cost of reporting, organizational structure of the firm, and CG.

- **Regulatory oversight:** An organization’s voluntary reporting is by-and-large influenced by legislation, accounting norms, and market regulations. These regulations can be ‘coercive’ in nature and the State can exercise its coercive powers directly, or indirectly. It exercises its powers ‘directly’ by enacting laws and regulations that guide the reporting of financial information (Bhasin, 2011). The State exercises its coercive powers ‘indirectly’ through institutions, or by establishing certain governmental policies. Sometimes, coercive powers can also be exercised by the parent corporation onto its subsidiary, by a major supplier, by customers or by labor unions. Voluntary reporting can also be affected by the ‘informal’ rules adopted by the organization like culture and customs of the firm. Professionals (such as accountants) also influence the level of voluntary reporting since they are often called-upon to interpret certain reporting rules. Their advice has the effect of normalizing the application of reporting rules.
- **Market forces:** Market forces can be divided into two sub-categories: ‘capital- market’ forces and ‘labor-market’ forces. As it relates to capital market forces, “there is a positive relationship between disclosing information to investors and stock prices.” This is due to the fact that the corporation is managing the expectation of its investors and avoiding surprises and volatility. In addition, public information increases investor wealth by decreasing the level of asymmetric information. When relating to labor market forces, managers will tend to disclose information that increases their

reputation as good managers and thus increase their remuneration. They will also tend to delay disclosing 'bad' news but immediately disclose 'good' news (Bhasin, 2011a).

- **Cost of reporting:** From an 'economical' perspective, managers will only disclose information "if the advantages of such reporting exceed the cost of disclosing the information" (Bhasin, 2011b). The corporations must bear the 'direct' cost of disclosing the information to the public, and those costs are not 'negligible'. There are two types of direct cost: preparation and analysis of financial statements. The first, direct-cost is borne by the corporation, while the second, direct-cost is borne by the 'user' of the information. Another type of cost related to the reporting of information is the effect of such reporting on 'competition'. As Bhasin (2011c) stated "Corporations argue that "divulging sensitive information to the public decreases their competitive edge, since their competitors can glean more information on the inner workings of the corporation." The corporation also bears 'legal' costs related to the non-reporting of information. In effect, the non-reporting of information will trigger 'legal-penalties' and the corporation will have to 'restate' its publicly disclosed information to reflect this new information, which will increase the 'overall' cost of reporting. There is also the 'political' cost. In effect, the political environment of the corporation affects its level of reporting. A corporation with 'high-visibility' on the political spectrum will "wish to diminish its level of reporting in order to avoid sparking the interest of the government."
- **Organizational factors:** The structure of the organization establishes 'routines' and 'procedures' for identifying and responding to certain reporting problems. "There are three main factors within the corporation that determine the level of reporting: the 'culture', the 'strategy' of the corporation, and the 'internal' politics of the firm. The 'personality' of the person in charge of reporting will also influence the level of reporting of the corporation," (Bhasin, 2012). A more conservative person will have "a ritualistic approach to reporting while a more dynamic person will have an opportunistic approach to reporting."
- **Corporate governance:** The 'concentration' of shareholders does not seem to be a factor that affects the level of voluntary reporting. However, recent studies have suggested that "the level of voluntary reporting of the corporation will be higher if the dominant group of shareholders is composed of outsiders." Conversely, if the dominant group of shareholders is composed of insiders, the level of reporting will be lower. However, in light of increased attention to CG matters, many companies have created separate Web-pages devoted exclusively to CG matters, such as information about the board of directors and committees. The Internet has helped to promote transparency, liquidity and efficiency in capital markets (Bhasin, 2012a).

No doubt, information reporting is an important and efficient means of protecting shareholders and is at the heart of CG. Frankly speaking, voluntary reporting by a corporation is a most powerful 'communication' tool. For example, Collett (2005) asserts that "CG issues have become so significant that it is likely firms may use information about them for 'impression' management." Appropriate corporate reporting systems means that a 'good' corporation is able to impress the markets with its integrity. As Bhasin and Shaikh (2013c) remarked, "New regulations, new requirements and ever-increasing demands for transparency determine corporations to follow the recent trends in corporate reporting in order to comply with 'best practice' regulations: narrative reporting, balance in the structure of the reports, inclusion of management report, reporting CG and social responsibility, balancing financial and non-financial information, comparability over time, etc." The quality of financial and non-financial reporting, however, depends significantly on the 'robustness' of the reporting standards on the basis of which the financial/non-financial information is prepared and reported. "In addition, reporting indicates the quality of the firm's product and business model, its growth strategy and market positioning, as well as the risks it is facing" (Chahine and Filatotchev, 2008).

5. Clause 49 of the Listing Agreement

The term 'Clause 49' refers to clause number 49 of the Listing Agreement between a corporation and the stock exchanges on which it is listed. The listing agreement is identical for all Indian stock exchanges, including the NSE and BSE. This clause was added to the Listing Agreement in late 2000 consequent to the

recommendations of the Birla Committee on CG constituted by the “Securities Exchange Board of India (SEBI)” in 1999. Clause 49, when it was first added, was intended to introduce some basic CG practices in Indian corporations and brought in a number of key changes in governance and reporting (many of which we take for granted today). As Patel (2006) states: “It specified the minimum number of independent directors required on the board of a corporation. The setting up of an Audit committee, and a Shareholders’ Grievance committee, among others, were made mandatory as were the Management’s Discussion & Analysis section and the Report on Corporate Governance in the Annual Report, and reporting of fees paid to non-executive directors. A limit was placed on the number of committees that a director could serve on.” In late 2002, the SEBI constituted the Murthy Committee to “assess the adequacy of current CG practices and to suggest improvements.” Based on the recommendations of this committee, SEBI issued a modified Clause 49 on October 29, 2004 (the ‘revised Clause 49’) which came into operation on January 1, 2006.

The revised Clause 49 has suitably pushed forward the original intent of protecting the interests of investors through enhanced governance practices and reporting. For example, Bhasin (2013) briefly described them as: “Five broad themes predominate: the independence criteria for directors have been clarified; the roles and responsibilities of the board have been enhanced; the quality and quantity of reporting have improved; the roles and responsibilities of the audit committee in all matters relating to internal controls and financial reporting have been consolidated; and the accountability of top management (specifically the CEO and CFO) has been enhanced.” Within each of these areas, the revised Clause 49 moves further into the realm of global best practices (and sometimes, even beyond). As Chakrabarti (2008) states: “Similar in spirit and scope to the Sarbanes-Oxley measures in the USA, Clause 49 has clearly been a milestone in the evolution of CG practices in India.” The revised Clause 49 has suitably pushed forward the original intent of protecting the interests of investors through enhanced governance practices and reporting. Corporate managers and investors agree that while it can be argued that complying with these requirements involves a significant amount of effort, there can be no doubt that these are an essential step towards bringing Indian capital-markets and governance standards in line with the rest of the world. No doubt, the quality and quantity of reporting have improved.

“India has the largest number of listed corporations in the world, and the efficiency and well-being of the financial markets is critical for the economy in particular and the society as a whole. It is imperative to design and implement a dynamic mechanism of CG, which protects the interests of relevant stakeholders without hindering the growth of enterprises,” (Bhasin, 2013a). With the SEBI guidelines (Clause 49) demanding the listed Indian corporations to adopt and follow the CG norms, it became necessary for every organization to ensure higher shareholder and stakeholder values. The SEBI envisages that all these CG norms will be enforced through listing agreements between corporations and the stock exchanges. A little reflection suggests that for corporations with little floating stock delisting because of non-compliance is hardly a credible threat. The SEBI can, of course, counter that by stating that the reputation effect of delisting can induce compliance and, hence, better CG. Thus, what is needed a small corpus of legally mandated rules, buttressed by a much larger body of self-regulation and voluntary compliance. For example, Sharma and Singh (2009) asserts: “It is now mandatory for the corporations to file with the SEBI, the CG compliance report, shareholding pattern along with the financial statements. The SEBI has created a separate link known as “Edifar” to post the relevant information submitted by the corporation.”

Bhasin (2013b) observed, “Public corporations in India face a ‘fragmented’ regulatory structure. The Companies Act is administered by the Ministry of Corporate Affairs (MCA) and is currently enforced by the Company Law Board (CLB). The MCA, the SEBI, and the stock exchanges share jurisdiction over ‘listed’ corporations, with the MCA being the ‘primary’ government body charged with administering the Companies Act of 1956, while SEBI has served as the securities market ‘regulator’ since 1992.” However, Afsharipour (2011) very aptly sums up the situation as: “Like CG standards in the U.S. and the U.K., India’s CG reforms followed a fiduciary and agency cost model. With a focus on the agency model of CG, the Clause 49 reforms included detailed rules regarding the role and structure of the corporate board and internal controls.”

Recently, the Companies Act was enacted on August, 2013 which provides for major overhaul of CG norms for all companies. “The Companies Act 2013 envisages radical changes in the area of CG and is set to have far reaching implications. Securities Exchange Board of India (SEBI), with the objective to align with the provisions of the Companies Act 2013, issued a revised Clause 49 to adopt best CG practices and to make CG norms more effective,” (Bhasin, 2013c). The revised Clause came into effect from October 1, 2014 except for the clause relating to the constitution of a risk management committee which shall apply to the top 100 listed companies by market capitalization, as at the end of the immediate previous financial year. According to Deloitte study (2015), “The Companies Act, 2013 has raised the bar for the Boards in India. The new concepts introduced in the Act such like women directors on the Boards to bring in gender diversity, enhanced reporting norms, small shareholder director, performance evaluation of Boards and directors, mandating corporate social responsibility, introducing the possibility of class actions; including internal financial controls and risk management as a part of oversight of the Boards and enhancing the role of the Independent Directors aim at enhancing the protection for minority shareholders, provide for investor protection and activism, a better framework for insolvency regulation and thus strengthen the foundations of good governance in Indian companies.” A comparison of the provisions of CG under revised Clause 49 and Companies Act, 2013 is briefly summarized below:

Particulars	Revised Clause 49	Companies Act, 2013
Woman director	Have to be complied with effect from October 1, 2014.	It provides one year transition period to comply with the requirement.
Limit on number of directorship for independent directors	Maximum 7 listed companies as independent director except where such person is WTD; the limit is up to 3 directorships.	The 2013 Act provides overall limits on the number of directorships by an individual i.e. maximum 20 companies (including 10 public companies). However, no specific limit is prescribed for independent directors.
Tenure of independent director	The maximum tenure of an independent director is capped at 10 years. However, if a person who has already served as an independent director for 5 years or more on 1 Oct. 2014, will be eligible for appointment for a term of 5 years only.	The overall term of an independent director is 10 years, except that under the 2013 Act, these requirements are applied prospectively.
Constitution of Audit Committee	Two-thirds of the members of the AC shall be independent directors. The chairman of the AC is to be an independent director.	The AC is to be formed with majority being independent directors i.e. more than half of the board to be independent. No specific requirement for the chairman to be an independent director.
Related Party Transactions	All material related party transactions shall require approval of the shareholders through special resolution and the related party shall abstain from voting on such resolutions.	All related party transactions which are not in the ordinary course of business or not at arm’s length basis should also be approved by the board and shareholders. However, shareholders’ approval is required for only certain transactions with the criteria for such approval defined differently.
Risk Management Committee	The revised clause 49 inserts a new requirement (for only top 100 listed companies by market capitalization as at the end of the immediate previous financial year) that a company shall also constitute a risk management committee.	The 2013 Act does not contain similar requirements.
Separation of offices of chairman and chief executive officer	No explicit provision earlier. Introduced as a non-mandatory provision.	Separation required unless articles of the company permit otherwise or the company does not has multiple businesses.

6. Literature Review

Undoubtedly, 'transparency' is an important component of a well-functioning system of CG and corporate reporting to stakeholders is the 'principal' means by which corporations can become transparent (Bhasin, 2009). Unfortunately, most of the developing countries do not have a 'strong' policy on 'voluntary' CG reporting and financial accounting reporting. Our literature review found some prior studies that looked at CG reporting practices of both developed and developing countries. Some of the primary research studies relating to CG reporting are briefly reviewed below.

Collett and Hraskey (2005) analyzed the relationships between voluntary disclosure of CG information by the corporations and their intention to raise capital in the financial markets. A sample of 299 corporations listed on the 'Australian' stock exchanges had been taken for the year 1994. The study found out that "only 29 Australian corporations made voluntary CG disclosure, and the degree of disclosures were varied from corporation to corporation." Similarly, Barako et al., (2006) examined the extent of voluntary disclosures made by the 'Kenyan' companies and from 1992 to 2001. The results revealed that "the audit committee was a significant factor associated with level of voluntary disclosure, while the proportion of non-executive directors on the board was negatively associated." A study done by Maingot and Zeghal (2008) reported about the disclosure of governance information by the 8 'Canadian' banks. Their analysis indicates that "the bigger the bank, the more disclosure there is. Overall, their results suggest that the choices to disclose and the extent of disclosure are influenced by the strategic considerations of management."

In another study conducted by Hossain and Hammami (2009), the researchers' examined the determinants of voluntary disclosure in the AR of 25 listed firms of Doha Securities Market in 'Qatar.' A disclosure checklist of 44 voluntary items was developed and statistical analysis was performed using multiple regression analysis. Their findings indicate that "age, size, complexity, and assets-in-place are significant and other variable profitability is insignificant in explaining the level of voluntary disclosure." Elsayed and Hoque (2010), identified a set of perceived international 'environmental factors' and examined how these factors influence a corporation's voluntary disclosure levels. Based on the data collected from 100 'Egyptian' non-financial listed companies, the results of multiple-regression analysis indicated that "the level of a corporation's voluntary disclosure is positively and significantly associated with its perceived influence." Moreover, Zhang et al., (2011) in their 'Chinese' study empirically analyzed the impact of CG structure, operation situation and external environments on the voluntary disclosure of Chinese electronic listed companies' information. Their findings suggest that "the share ratio of circulation stock, percentages of independent directors, separation of chairman of the board and CEO, corporation size and profitability are significantly positively related to voluntary disclosure level."

According to a research study undertaken by Ntim et al., (2012) constructed a voluntary CG disclosure index from the 2002 King Report using a sample of 169 'South African' listed corporations from 2002 to 2006. The authors concluded that "block ownership is negatively associated with voluntary CG disclosure, while board size, audit firm size, cross-listing, the presence of a CG committee, government ownership and institutional ownership are positively related to voluntary CG disclosure." Similarly, Al-Moataz and Hussainey (2012) examined the relation between some CG mechanisms and the disclosure-level of CG information in the 'Saudi Arabian' listed companies. It used a sample of 97 financial reports of listed companies in 2006 and 2007 and used the content analysis approach. The authors found that "board independence, audit committee size, profitability, liquidity and gearing are the main determinants of CG disclosure." A study by Mamun and Kamardin (2014) aimed to explore the corporate voluntary disclosure practices of the listed banks in Bangladesh. Results show that the extent of voluntary disclosure significantly improved from 2005 to 2008. However, the level of disclosure items related to CG and risk management are lower than other disclosure categories. According to a study undertaken by Naveed, Khurshid and Shakeel (2015), they analyzed the impact of different governance related variables on the CG disclosure level of Pakistani manufacturing firms. The study period is 2014 and used a sample of 50 manufacturing firms which are classified into five different categories.

Similarly, Elshandy and Neri (2015) examined the influence of CG on risk disclosure practices in the UK and Italy, and studied the impact of those practices on market liquidity. The authors found that strongly governed firms in the UK tend to provide more meaningful risk information to their investors than weakly governed firms. However, Srairi (2015) investigated the impact of the level of CG disclosure on bank performance by constructing a CG disclosure index for 27 Islamic banks operating in five Arab-Gulf countries, using content analysis on the banks' annual reports for 3 years (2011-2013). The findings related to countries revealed that only two countries, the United Arab Emirates and Bahrain, possess a higher level of CG Disclosure Index. Recently, a study undertaken by Forte et al., (2016) aimed to investigate the factors influencing the level of voluntary disclosure by companies in the Brazilian banking sector. The sample was composed of the 100 largest Brazilian banks in relation to total assets in 2012 and used multiple linear regression methodology. The evidence revealed that "the corporate reputation and the size of the companies had a significant and positive relationship with the level of voluntary disclosure." Similarly, Elmagrhi et al., (2016) investigated the level of compliance with, and disclosure of, good CG practices among UK publicly listed firms. The results suggest that there is a substantial variation in the levels of compliance with, and disclosure of, good CG practices among the sampled UK firms. Firms with larger board size, more independent outside directors and greater director diversity tend to disclose more CG information voluntarily, whereas the level of voluntary CG compliance and disclosure is insignificantly related to the existence of a separate CG committee and institutional ownership.

Even though, most of the developing countries do not have strong policy on voluntary CG disclosures, India as a developing country has not fallen behind. We found a limited number of studies that looked at CG disclosure practices in Indian companies, with some relevance to our study. Some of the reported research studies undertaken by the researchers' from India relating to the CG disclosures are briefly reviewed below.

Gupta, Nair and Gogula (2003) analyzed the CG reporting practices of 30 selected 'Indian' corporations listed in BSE. The CG section of the Annual Reports for the years 2001-02 and 2002-03 had been analyzed by using the content analysis, and least square regression technique was used for data analysis. Their study found "variations in the reporting practices of the corporations, and in certain cases, omission of mandatory requirements as per Clause 49." Similarly, Bhattacharya and Rao (2005) examined whether adoption of Clause 49 predicts lower volatility and returns for large Indian firms. They compared a one-year period after adoption (starting June 1, 2001) to a similar period before adoption (starting June 1, 1998). The logic is that Clause 49 should improve reporting and thus reduce information asymmetry and thereby reduce share price volatility. The authors found "insignificant results for volatility and mixed results for returns." In another study undertaken by Subramanian (2006, 2014), the author identified the differences in reporting pattern of financial information and governance attributes. A sample of 90 corporations from BSE-100 index, NSE Nifty had been taken for the financial year 2003-04. The study used the Standard & Poor's Transparency and Reporting Survey Questionnaire for collection of data. The study finally concluded that "there were no differences in reporting pattern of public-private sector corporations, as far as financial transparency and information reporting were concerned."

Similarly, K. C. Gupta (2006) traced out the differences in CG practices of few local corporations of an automobile industry. The data with respect to governance practices had been collected from the annual reports of the corporations for the year 2004-05. The study "did not observe significant deviations of actual governance practices from Clause 49." A study by Hossain and Reaz (2007) reported the results of an empirical investigation of the extent of voluntary reporting by 38 listed banking companies in 'India'. It also reported the results of the association between corporation-specific characteristics and voluntary reporting of the sample companies. Their study revealed that "Indian banks are disclosing a considerable amount of voluntary information." In another study conducted by Rathod and Dalvadi (2008), the authors stated: "The annual reports of 20 companies have been selected randomly from the list of 400 companies and their Annual Reports are thoroughly studied in respect to reporting of non-statutory information (both accounting and non-accounting)." Sareen and Chander (2009) examined the relationship between corporation attributes and extent of CG reporting. An index of CG reporting consisting of 85 items was constructed. The findings of their study exhibited "a positive relationship between selected corporation attributes and extent of CG

reporting.” As per a study conducted by Pahuja and Bhatia (2010), the researchers attempted to determine the extent to which ‘Indian’ listed-companies disclose their CG practices by examining the annual reports of 50 listed companies. They concluded that “there is a substantial scope for improvement in the CG reporting practices and the size of the corporation is a significant determinant of reporting.”

Bhasin (2011) conducted an exploratory ‘case-study’ of the Reliance Industries Limited, and developed his model as a “working method”. In order to ascertain how far this corporation was in compliant of CG standards, a “point-value-system” was applied. Based on the reporting made by the corporation in its Annual Report for the year 2006-07 the results reveals that “RIL had shown very good performance, with an overall score of 85 points. Moreover, RIL group is in the forefront of implementation of “best CG practices in India,” but some scope still exists for its improvement.” In a study done by Subramanyam and Dasaraju (2014), they attempted to analyze the level of reporting on CG practices among the biggest IT companies in India in from 2004-2005 to 2011-2012 and its effects on performance and profitability. Using the survey of 6 IT companies with the Standard & Poor’s score card to assess the CGD practices of the companies as a benchmark. It is observed that among the sample IT companies, Infosys, Wipro, TCS and HCL scored high score i.e. more than 100 and Tech Mahindra and Mphasis scored low score i.e. less than 96 in corporate governance reporting practices.

A research study by Madhani (2015) used a voluntary reporting index and hand-collected governance and reporting data for final sample of 54 firms. In this study, the CGD score of firms listed in BSE are measured by doing content analysis of annual report of sample firms. Study found that board committees are major contributor to overall corporate governance and reporting practices of firms. Moreover, according to study conducted by Sachdeva, Batra and Walia (2015), the authors attempted to calculate CG scores for thirty different companies selected on the basis of BSE-30 as on march 2013. The selected score has been calculated for seven years period, i.e., 2005 to 2012. Corporate Governance index has also been calculated for the selected sample companies. They concluded as “it is seen that there is increase in the average score and in CG index as well in case of all the companies.”

The aforesaid review of studies reveals that there is an urgent need to study the “voluntary” CG reporting practices followed by the corporations in India. The study of VCGR practices has remained as an untouched phenomenon yet. Therefore, the study of VCGR practices assumes significance at this evolving stage of CG in India. This paper attempts to study “the VCGR practices followed by the corporations over and above the mandatory requirements.” Besides, this study has been planned with the following two ‘specific’ objectives in mind: (a) to examine the voluntary CG reporting practices of ‘selected’ companies, and (b) to measure the ‘extent of variation’ in the reporting pattern of CG practices of the corporations under study.

7. Significance and Time Period of the Study

In India, the question of CG has assumed importance mainly in the wake of economic liberalization, deregulation of industry and business, as also the demand for a new corporate ethos and stricter compliance with the legislation. However, there have been several leading CG initiatives launched in India since the mid-1990s. The first was by the CII, which came up with the first “voluntary” code of CG in 1998. As Sarkar (2009) remarked: “In 1996, CII took a special initiative on CG—the first institutional initiative in Indian industry.” In April 1998, India produced the first substantial code of best practice on CG after the start of the Asian financial crisis in mid-1997. Titled “Desirable CG: A Code”, this document was written not by the government, but by the Confederation of Indian Industries (www.ciionline.org). It is one of the few codes in Asia that explicitly discusses domestic CG problems and seeks to apply best-practice ideas to their solution.

The next big move was by the SEBI, now enshrined as Clause 49 (very similar to the U.S. Sarbanes-Oxley Act, 2002) of the listing agreement. In late 1999, a government-appointed committee under the leadership of Shri Kumar Mangalam Birla (Chairman, Aditya Birla Group) released a draft of India’s first national code (Clause 49) on CG for listed companies. The code, however, was approved by the Securities Exchange

Board of India (SEBI) in early 2000 and was implemented in stages over the following two years (applying first to newly listed and large companies). It also led to changes in the stock exchange listing rules. The Naresh Chandra Committee and Narayana Murthy Committee reports followed it in 2002. Based on some of the recommendation of these two committees, SEBI further revised the Clause 49 of the listing agreement in August 2004. Therefore, for the purpose of this study, “an intermediate period of two years from 2003-04 and 2004-05 was found to be most appropriate,” and finally selected. The primary objective was to examine the extent of VCGR by the sampled companies during this intermediate period. No doubt, once that period of VCGR is over, all the companies are required to make ‘mandatory’ reporting, as per Clause 49, corporation law and accounting standards. This paper contributes to literature on reporting and CG in two important ways. First, it provides evidence on the determinants of CG reporting in a developing country, like India. Second, it offers some insights into CG mechanisms and corporate characteristics that significantly drive the reporting of CG information.

8. Research Method

For the purpose of this study, we have taken a sample of 50 listed Indian corporations for a period of two years, i.e., 2003-04 and 2004-05. These corporations were selected on the basis of “average” sales for a period of four years starting from 2000-01 to 2003-04. Accordingly, the data with respect to the sales figures were extracted from Prowess database of Centre for Monitoring Indian Economy. ‘Ranking’ method was used for selection of the corporations and the first 15 corporations having highest sales figures have been included in the sample. Hence, the total number of selected corporations was 60, but due to the non-availability of annual reports of few corporations, the sample was finally restricted to 50 corporations.

Over the last decade, the “content analysis” has been widely used by several leading researchers to study the CG performance and reporting (Beattie and Thomas, 2006). Therefore, as part of this study, “content analysis” has been used to analyze the extent of voluntary CG reporting by the 50 companies. Indeed, this involves ‘codification’ of qualitative and quantitative information into pre-defined categories in order to derive patterns in the presentation and reporting of information (Bhasin, 2011). Moreover, the coding process involved reading the Annual Report of each corporation and coding the information according to pre-defined categories of CG reporting. By looking at the reporting within the Annual Report, one can examine the extent to which Indian corporations publicly documented the presence (or importance) of CG. The data with respect to CG practices of the corporations have been collected from the Annual Reports of the corporations from Web-sites, as well as, Prowess database. Our sample of 50 corporations comprised of corporations drawn from four industries, viz., software, textiles, sugar and paper. **Table-2** shows the industry-wise break up of our sample of study.

Table-2: Industry-wise Classification of Sampled Corporations

S. No.	Industry	No. of Corporations	Percentage
1	Software	12	24
2	Textiles	14	28
3	Sugar	13	26
4	Paper	11	22
	Total	50	100

9. Voluntary Corporate Governance Reporting (VCGR) Index

In order to examine the voluntary corporate governance reporting (VCGR) practices of the sampled 50 corporations, the CG section of the Annual Report has been analyzed. Moreover, the online information was taken from the CG Web-page and through the AR and the proxy circulars. Also, a coding sheet was developed to evaluate the CG reporting of our sample. Finally, a voluntary “CG Reporting Index” has been prepared by selecting 40 items from the CG section of the Annual Reports of these corporations. For the purposes of this study, “all the CG items have been divided under the seven dimensions, viz., board of directors (7 items), meetings (4 items), formation of committees (8 items), CG initiatives (5 items), compliance reports of review committees (8 items), and shareholders and others (7 items).” **Annexure-1**

shows the item-wise voluntary CG reporting score, categorized under seven sub-heads, during 2003-04 and 2004-05. The contents of Index have been compared with the voluntary CG practices, if any, followed by the corporation, and awarded a score of '1' for following a particular item, or '0' for otherwise. Descriptive statistics, i.e., mean, standard deviation and coefficient of variation have been applied for the analysis. Moreover, Kruskal-Wallis Test has been applied to see the significance of difference of reporting among the industries.

In order to study the voluntary CG reporting practices of each corporation, reporting score has been arrived at as follows:

Voluntary Governance Score of a Corporation =

$$\frac{\text{Total Score Gained by a Corporation}}{\text{No. of Items in the Index}} \times 100$$

10. Findings and Analysis of the Results

Table-3 presents the corporation-wise VCGD scores and practices for two years. During 2003, the Infosys Limited occupied the first rank in the reporting index (35%), followed by Bajaj Hindustan Limited (30%), ITC Limited (22.5%), GTL Limited (17.5%), EID Parry (India) Limited (15%), Reliance Industries Limited (12.5%), Polaris Software Lab Limited (10%), Garden Silk Mills Limited (10%), Rajasthan Spinning Mills Limited (10%), Oudh Sugar Mills Limited (10%), Sirpur Paper Mills Limited (10%), Rolta India Limited (7.5%), Arvind Mills Limited (7.5%), S. Kumars Nationwide Limited (7.5%), Raymond Limited (7.5%), and so on.

Table-3: Voluntary Corporate Governance Reporting Score by Corporations

S. No.	Industry/Corporation Name	2003-04		2004-05	
		No. of Items Scored	Score in %	No. of Items Scored	Score in %
A	Software				
1	GTL Ltd.	7	17.5	8	20.0
2	HCLTechnologies Ltd.	1	2.5	1	2.5
3	IFLEX Solutions Ltd.	1	2.5	1	2.5
4	Igate Global Solutions Ltd.	1	2.5	1	2.5
5	Infosys Ltd.	14	35.0	18	45.0
6	Larsen & Toubro Ltd.	1	2.5	1	2.5
7	Mascon Global Ltd.	1	2.5	1	2.5
8	Pentamedia Graphics Ltd.	0	0	0	0
9	Polaris Software Lab Ltd.	4	10.0	6	15.0
10	Rolta India Ltd.	3	7.5	3	7.5
11	Satyam Computer Services Ltd.	0	0	0	0
12	Wipro Ltd.	4	10.0	4	10.0
B.	Textiles				
13	Alok Industries Ltd.	1	2.5	1	2.5
14	Arvind Mills Ltd.	3	7.5	4	10.0
15	Bombay Dyeing & Mfg. Ltd.	0	0	0	0
16	Century Enka Ltd.	2	5.0	2	5.0
17	Eskay K'N'It Ltd.	0	0	0	0
18	Garden Silk Mills Ltd.	4	10.0	4	10.0
19	Indian Rayon & Industries Ltd.	1	2.5	1	2.5
20	Indo Rama Synthetics Ltd.	1	2.5	1	2.5
21	Mahavir Spinning Mills Ltd.	1	2.5	1	2.5
22	Nahar Spinning Mills Ltd.	2	5.0	3	7.5
23	Rajasthan Spinning Mills Ltd.	4	10.0	4	10.0
24	Raymond Ltd.	3	7.5	3	7.5
25	Reliance Industries Ltd.	5	12.5	4	10.0
26	S. Kumars Nationwide Ltd.	3	7.5	3	7.5
C.	Sugar				
27	Andhra Sugars Ltd.	0	0	0	0
28	Bajaj Hindustan Ltd.	12	30.0	12	30.0
29	Balrampur Chinni Mills Ltd.	1	2.5	1	2.5
30	Bannari Amman Sugars Ltd.	1	2.5	1	2.5
31	DCM Shriram Industries Ltd.	0	0	0	0
32	EID Parry India Ltd.	6	15.0	7	17.5
33	Jeypore Sugar Ltd.	0	0	0	0
34	Oudh Sugar Mills Ltd.	4	10.0	4	10.0
35	Sakthi Sugars Ltd.	1	2.5	1	2.5
36	Saraswati Industrial Syndicate Ltd.	0	0	0	0
37	Simbhaoli Sugar Mills Ltd.	1	2.5	1	2.5
38	Ugar Sugar Works Ltd.	0	0	0	0
39	Upper Ganges Sugar Ltd.	3	7.5	4	10.0
D.	Paper				
40	Andhra Pradesh Paper Mills Ltd.	1	2.5	1	2.5
41	Century Textiles & Industries Ltd.	0	0	0	0
42	ITC Ltd.	9	22.5	8	20.0
43	JK Paper Ltd.	2	5	2	5
44	Pudumjee Pulp & Paper Mills Ltd.	1	2.5	1	2.5
45	Seshasayee Paper Boards Ltd.	1	2.5	1	2.5
46	Shreyan Industries Ltd.	0	0	0	0
47	Sirpur Paper Mills Ltd.	4	10.0	4	10.0
48	Star Paper Mills Ltd.	0	0	0	0
49	Tamil Nadu Newsprint & Paper Mills Ltd.	0	0	0	0
50	West Coast Paper Mills Ltd.	1	2.5	1	2.5

(Source: Compiled by the author from the Annual Reports of the Selected Corporations)

Unfortunately, there were several corporations like Pentmedia Graphics Limited, Satyam Computer Services Limited, Eskay K’N’It Limited, Bombay Dyeing and Manufacturing Limited, etc., which are having ‘zero’ score on voluntary governance index, revealing that these corporations are not following the CG practices beyond the mandatory requirements.

Similarly, in 2004-05, again maximum reporting was made by the Infosys Limited (45%), followed by Bajaj Hindustan Limited (30%), ITC Limited (20%), EID Parry (India) Limited (17.5%), Polaris Software Lab Limited (15%), Garden Silk Mills Limited (12.5%), Wipro Limited (10%), Arvind Mills Limited (10%), Rajasthan Spinning Mills Limited (10%), Reliance Industries Limited (10%), Oudh Sugar Mills Limited (10%), Sirpur Paper Mills Limited (10%), and so on. Unfortunately, Satyam Computer Services Limited, Eskay K’N’It Limited, Bombay Dyeing and Manufacturing Limited, Century Enka Limited, Saraswati Industrial Syndicate Limited, Jeypore Sugar Mills Limited, Andhra Sugar Mills Limited, etc., were found not disclosing even a single item of the voluntary reporting index.

Table-4 depicts the industry-wise classification of reporting score through mean, standard deviation, and coefficient of variation. However, a quick glance of the table shows that the maximum mean reporting was of software (7.708) industry followed by sugar (5.577), textiles (5.357) and paper (4.318) industry in the year 2003-04. As far as standard deviation is concerned, software was having the significant variation in items (10.030) followed by sugar (8.329), paper (6.716) and textiles (3.905). However, average mean, standard deviation and coefficient of variation for the year 2003-04 were 5.74, 7.24 and 127, respectively.

Table-4: Industry-wise Classification of Reporting Score

S. No	Industry	Mean	2003-04		2004-05		
			Standard Deviation	Coefficient of Variation	Mean	Standard Deviation	Coefficient of variation
1.	Software	7.708	10.030	130.06	9.792	12.630	129.02
2.	Textiles	5.357	3.905	72.88	6.071	3.887	64.02
3.	Sugar	5.577	8.329	149.54	6.154	8.527	138.56
4.	Paper	4.318	6.716	155.54	4.091	6.049	147.86
	Average	5.740	7.240	127.00	6.530	7.773	119.86

(Source: Computed from the Voluntary CG Reporting Scores of Table-3.)

Similarly, during 2004-05, maximum mean reporting was done by software (9.792) industry followed by sugar (6.154), textiles (6.071) and paper (4.091). Unfortunately, the standard deviation was highest in case of software (12.630) industry, revealing the significant variation in the items, followed by sugar (8.527), paper (6.049) and textiles (3.887). However, average mean, standard deviation and coefficient of variation for the year 2004-05 were 6.53, 7.77 and 119.86, respectively.

From the above analysis, it is very much apparent that “the ‘software’ industry has performed extremely well for both the years of our study by disclosing the ‘maximum’ number of items of voluntary CG Reporting Index.” There was just one corporation, namely, “Infosys Limited” in the software industry, which was disclosing maximum number of voluntary items (14 (35%) in 2003-04 and 18 (45%) in 2004-05 out of total 40 items) beyond the mandatory requirements. Overall, there was an increase in the mean reporting score in the year 2005 from 5.740 to 6.530 in 2004, respectively. It means that the corporations were disclosing more voluntary governance items. However, software industry was having the highest mean values (7.708 and 9.792) for both the years; same is the case in respect of highest standard deviation (10.03 and 12.63). It means that the units are not concentrated around the mean values. However, similar was the case with the sugar industry, while the textile industry was having the low standard deviations (3.90 and 3.88) for both the years as compared to other industries.

Table-5: Extent of Variation in the Voluntary CG Reporting Score

Items Range (%)	2003-04	Percentage	2004-05	Percentage
0-10	38	76	36	72
10-20	9	18	10	20
20-30	1	2	2	4
30-40	2	4	1	2
40-50	0	0	1	2
50 or Above	0	0	0	0
Total	50	100	50	100

Table-5 reveals the extent of variation in the items as disclosed in the CG section of the Annual Reports. During 2003-04, 38 (76%) corporations had disclosed in the range of 0-10 items. About 9 (18%) of the corporations had disclosed 10-20% items, 1 (2%) of the corporations had disclosed 20-30% items and just 2 (4%) of sample corporations had disclosed in the range of 30-40%. However, the situation was more or less similar in 2004-05. It is worth mentioning here that during the two years of our study, two leading corporations, namely, Infosys Limited and Bajaj Hindustan Limited had disclosed more than 30% items of voluntary CG reporting index. Similarly, GTL Limited and ITC Limited were the second biggest disclosing corporations with reporting of 20% items of voluntary CG index. In the year 2004-05, there was an increase in the extent of reporting as 72% corporations have reported in the range of up to 10%. Now, 20% of corporations had started disclosing in the range of 10-20%. Once again, Infosys Limited had started disclosing in the range of 40-50%. So, it can be concluded from the above analysis that there was a slight improvement in the voluntary CG reporting score with slight variations. But overall reporting range of corporations was less than 50% of items in the CG reporting index, and hence, revealing the weak voluntary CG reporting practices followed up by these corporations. Their results suggested that “while compliance with and reporting of good CG practices varies substantially among the sampled companies, CG standards have generally improved over the study period examined.”

In order to examine whether there is a significant difference among the reporting score of the industries, we had applied Kruskal-Wallis. **Table-6** reveals the results of the Kruskal-Wallis test for both the time periods of study. It may be observed that there was no significant difference among the reporting scores of sampled industries for both the years. It means that most of the corporations in these industries were “disclosing voluntary CG practices at almost the same equivalent level.”

Table-6: Results of Kruskal-Wallis Test

Year	2003-04	2004-05
Chi-Square	2.840	3.483
Df	3.000	3.000
Sig.	0.417	0.323

11. Select Extracts from the Annual Reports about Voluntary CG Reporting

Some examples of voluntary CG reporting made by the leading Indian corporations in their Annual Reports for the year ended 2003-04 and 2004-05, from our sample of 50 companies, are given below:

Infosys Limited stated as: “Your Corporation continues to be a pioneer in benchmarking its CG policies with the best in the world. Our efforts are widely recognized by investors in India and abroad. Also, your Corporation is the first public Corporation in India to have undergone the “CG Audit” by Standard and Poor’s. Standard & Poor’s has rated your Corporation’s CG practices at CGS 8.6 on a scale of 10. Your Corporation has complied with all the recommendations of the Kumar Mangalam Birla Committee on CG constituted by the SEBI.” Similarly, Nandan Nilekani, Chief Executive Officer, President and Managing Director of Infosys Limited stated as, “Infosys has been a step ahead of the prevailing CG norms, implementing reforms before they became mandatory. Our reporting standards today are the best in the industry. We were ranked No. 1 in a CG Survey conducted by CLSA across Asia (excluding Japan). Infosys scored 87 percent against an average of 81 percent for the top 10 corporations. Infosys has maintained a top ranking in CG since 2001.”

Shri Mukesh Ambani, Chairman and Managing Director, Reliance Industries Limited described in Management Discussion and Analysis (MD&A) section as: “Reliance is one of the pioneers in the country in implementing the best international practices of CG. Reliance’s philosophy on CG envisages the attainment of the highest levels of transparency, accountability and equity, in all facets of its operations, and in all its interactions with its stakeholders, including shareholders, employees, the government and lenders. Reliance is committed to achieving the highest international standards of CG. In recognition of this pioneering effort, the Institute of Corporation Secretaries of India has bestowed on the Corporation the National Award for Excellence in CG for the year 2003. Reliance is in the forefront of implementation of CG best practices”

Shri Azim H. Premji, Chairman and Managing Director, Wipro Limited, stated as: “Your Corporation being a listed Corporation on the New York Stock Exchange also has a set of U.S. CG standards to follow which have recently being made more stringent with the passage of the Sarbanes-Oxley Act of 2002. Effective CG programs include the institution of corporate ombudsperson and encourage whistleblowers to dissent when the interests of the corporation are compromised. Good CG is the responsibility and privilege of each and every stakeholder. At Wipro Limited, our pursuit towards achieving good CG is an ongoing process, thereby ensuring integrity, transparency and accountability in all our dealings with our employees, shareholders, customers and the community at large. We believe that the constant effort to improve operational performance, guided by our values, forms the basis for good CG. CG is strongly driven by our values such as quality, commitment, customer orientation and integrity.”

Your Corporation believes that efficient CG requires a clear understanding of the respective roles of the Board and of Senior Management and their relationships with others in the corporate structure. Your Corporation has always practiced CG of the highest standards. This part, along with the chapters on Management Discussion & Analysis shows the compliance standard of your Corporation with respect to reporting mandated under both Indian as well as the U.S. law. Your corporation has also formally developed and adopted comprehensive guidelines on CG in January 2004 and the same is posted on Corporation’s website. Corporation has been given the Highest Shareholder Value Creation and Governance Rating of SVG1 by an independent rating agency, ICRA Limited. Your Corporation has also been awarded the Golden Peacock award for Excellence in CG by the Institute of Directors.”

Shri Manoj G. Tirodkar, Chairman and Managing Director, GTL Limited described as: “The GTL Corporation had been taking various initiatives to strengthen its system by adopting globally established CG practices. The important players in the system being the Board and Management, steps had been taken for strengthening these Institutions from time to time. The Corporation’s policy on CG is to make CG a way of life, inter alia, by institutionalizing CG through continual improvement of internal systems and customer satisfaction. By constituting a Board with a balanced mix of experts, forming an Operating Council with Senior Professionals, appointing a Professional CEO for heading the Council and putting in place systems and processes, the corporation has laid a strong foundation for making CG a way of life.”

Shri Shishir Bajaj, Chairman and Managing Director, Bajaj Hindusthan Limited observed as: “Your Corporation has continued its quest to follow the best CG practices towards building trust amongst shareholders, employees, customers, suppliers (including farmers) and diverse stakeholders on four key elements of CG—transparency, fairness, reporting and accountability. We in BHL follow the best CG practices aimed at maximizing value for shareholders, while ensuring fairness to all segments of stakeholders—customers, employees, investors, vendors, state and central governments, and society at large. Ensuring total transparency in operations and inspiring the confidence and trust of stakeholders in the way we manage the Corporation are of paramount importance to us in BHL. Both the promoters and managers at BHL constantly strive to function as sacred trustees on behalf of every shareholder, large or small. For BHL, CG is basic to the corporate conduct of business. The traditional values of honesty, integrity, customer-orientation and an abiding commitment to service have struck deep roots across the organization.

Shri Yogesh Chandra Deveshwar, Chairman, ITC Limited remarked as: “ITC has been one of the frontrunners in India to have put in place a formalized system of CG. ITC was the first corporation in India to get itself voluntarily rated for CG. The ICRA has assigned a CGR 2 rating to the CG practices of ITC, which denotes a High Level of CG.” Similarly, Arun Jain, Chairman and CEO, Polaris Software Lab Limited described as: “Polaris perceives CG as an endeavor for transparency, and a wholehearted approach towards establishing professional management, aimed at continuous enhancement of shareholders’ value. The Corporation Code of Conduct has been adopted by Polaris Software Lab Limited to comply with the applicable rules of the Stock Exchanges where the securities of the Corporation are listed. It is the policy of Polaris to conduct all its business in strictly ethical and legal manner and adhering to the standards of integrity, fair dealing and good CG. This Code is intended to supplement, but does not replace, the corporation-wide Code of Conduct and the policies referenced therein.”

Shri Praful A. Shah, Chairman and Managing Director, Garden Silk Mills Limited observed as: “Your Corporation continues to follow the principles of good CG. The Corporation has already constituted several committees of directors to assist the Board in good CG. Your Corporation’s commitment for effective CG is a continuous process to benchmark its efforts within accepted standards for the creation of golden and trustable value towards the shareholders. CG ensures fairness, transparency and integrity of the management. CG is a way of life, rather than a mere legal compulsion. It further inspires and strengthens investor’s confidence and commitment to the Corporation. The basic philosophy of CG in the Corporation is to achieve business excellence for long-term stakeholder value. We believe that sound CG is critical to enhance and retain stakeholders trust.”

Shri Arun Churiwal, MD, Rajasthan Spinning and Weaving Mills Limited described as: “CG is a reflection of culture, policies, relationship with stakeholders and commitment to values and is also about maximizing shareholders value legally, ethically and on a sustainable basis, while ensuring fairness to every stakeholder—our customers, employees, investors, vendors-service providers-partners, state and the community at large. Your Corporation always aims at ensuring unwavering focus on conducting its business in accordance with the highest ethical standards and professionalism in all areas of its business operations and sound CG practices. The adoption of such corporate practices—founded on principles of transparency, strong Board oversight and high levels of integrity ensures accountability of the persons in charge of the Corporation and brings benefits to investors, customers, creditors, employees and the society at large. The Corporation will continue to stand by these standards. And as it grows, RSWM Limited (RSWM) will diligently look to adopt new and best-in-class systems and procedures for enhancing CG Standards within the Corporation for increasing the stakeholder value. As a Corporation, which believes in implementing CG practices that go beyond meeting the letter of law, RSWM has adopted practices mandated in Clause 49 and has established procedures and systems to be fully compliant with it.”

12. Conclusion

The issues regarding CG have received major attention owing to their apparent importance for the economic health of companies, especially after plethora of corporate scams and debacles in the recent times (Bhasin, 2015a). Successive waves of corporate scandal have reshaped the landscape of CG around the world and continued to do so in 2016. Most observers believe that the Petrobras scandal in Brazil, Satyam and more recent incidents in India, Toshiba in Japan, and perhaps Volkswagen in Germany will have a substantial impact on CG in those countries as legislators, regulators, and institutional shareholders demand more tools to promote accountability and transparency from companies and their boards of directors. Effective reporting will communicate the company’s approach to CG in a way that readers can easily understand. Successful business communication has five characteristics: simplicity, brevity, clarity, relevance and a human touch. As a matter of principle, all the relevant information should be made available to the users in a cost-effective and timely way. The CG framework should promote transparent and efficient markets, be consistent with the rule of law, and clearly articulate the division of responsibilities among different supervisory, regulatory and enforcement authorities (OECD 2014). However, Clause 49 of the Listing Agreement in India requires all “listed” corporations to file every quarter a “Corporate Governance Report,”

along with other 'mandatory' and 'non-mandatory' requirements of reporting. Timely reporting of consistent, comparable, relevant and reliable information on corporate financial performance, therefore, is at the core of 'good' CG.

High ethical values can reduce costs to achieve a high CG standard and make it more sustainable. Improving CG is an issue of critical importance to India today and for future developments. The year 2014 is shaping up to be a year of dramatic governance changes for Indian companies, as boards will be tasked with adding new committees and diversifying board membership and the periodic rotation of a company's external auditor will become mandatory (Bhasin, 2016). While significant improvements have been effected in required standards of CG, there is also some concern regarding overly increasing compliance and regulatory costs and efforts for companies as well as their independent directors. Among the major provisions of the Act are those of restraining voting rights of interested shareholders on related party transactions, recognition of board accountability to stakeholders besides shareholders, and extension of several good governance requirements to relatively large unlisted corporations (Balasubramanian, 2014). The Indian government has realized that good CG is necessary to improve corporate competitiveness and to attract foreign investors. It is believed that with better CG, listed firms can reduce agency costs, become more competitive in global markets, and fulfill their social responsibilities. Similarly, FASB Steering Committee Report concluded as: "Many leading corporations are voluntarily disclosing an extensive amount of business information that appears to be useful in communicating information to investors. The importance of voluntary reporting is expected to increase in the future because of the fast pace of change in the business environment." Corporate India witnessed the burgeoning economic growth since the 1990s that brought to the forefront the need for Indian companies to adopt corporate governance standards and practices, which are in line with international guidelines (Shrivastav and Kalsie, 2015).

A sample of 50 listed corporations has been taken for the purpose of the present study for a period of two years, i.e., 2003-04 and 2004-05. The results of this study also suggest that while compliance with and reporting of CG practices varies substantially among the sampled companies, CG standards have generally improved over the period. We can also conclude that there is a substantial scope for improvement in the CG reporting practices and the size of the corporation is a significant determinant of reporting. It can be concluded from the foregoing analysis that even though there is a slight improvement in the voluntary CG reporting score of the 50 corporations, yet it is considered to be a 'poor' reporting. Furthermore, the degree of reporting score and number of items disclosed varies from corporation to corporation and across industries. Broadly speaking, corporations are following less than 50% of the items of voluntary CG index taken for the study. There are a few items, such as, risk management, whistle-blowing policy and code of conduct for directors and senior management personnel, which have become the part of the revised clause 49 of the Listing Agreement effective from 2005-06. Undoubtedly, there is an urgent need to extend the scope of existing mandatory clause further by covering the items from VCGD index, so that the Indian CG standards could be at par with the international level. However, the limitations of the study are: the sample-size is limited to four industries and 50 corporations only; and the period of the study is limited up to two years only. Other researchers may find different inferences by extending the time period beyond two years.

Also, it is observed by Subramanyam and Dasaraju (2014) that "Infosys, Wipro, TCS and HCL scored high score, i.e., more than 100 and Tech Mahindra and Mphasis scored low score i.e. less than 96 in corporate governance reporting practices. To policy makers and practitioners, the results suggest that corporate governance should be monitored." Recently, Gupta (2015) sought to examine the extent of compliance/non-compliance of these norms by the listed companies to ascertain whether the corporate sector is complying with the regulatory norms in letters or in spirit. The study found "a not too encouraging response." To sum up, Bhasin (2016) concludes, "The results of present study speak directly to the debate on the choice between formal corporate governance regulations versus informal self-regulation. While the voluntary approach offers more flexibility and is globally more popular, questions have been raised about its effectiveness in promoting desirable governance practices." According to Reynolds (2016), "Around the world, large institutional investors continue to push hard for reforms that will enable them to elect independent non-executive directors who will constructively challenge management on strategy and hold

executives accountable for performance (and pay them accordingly). When trust breaks down, activist investors (often hedge funds) move in to drive for change, often with institutional support.”

If we want “robust and effective CG, we need robust and well-crafted rules, and vigorously enforcing them.” Indeed, CG stems from the culture and mindset of management, and cannot be regulated by legislation alone. Too many legal provisions and their intricacies would make the real objective worthless. Still much work remains to be done in India and the ethos of CG culture has yet to sink in. Full convergence with international CG reporting norms, accounting and audit standards, protection of minority investors, stronger enforcement of existing laws & regulations, etc., are some of the ‘grey’ areas requiring immediate improvements. Moves are afoot globally to promote ‘convergence’ of CG reporting practices. Moreover, the importance of voluntary reporting is expected to increase in the future because of the fast pace of change in the business environment. In nutshell, we can say that “CG reporting scenario in India remains at best a gradual work-in-progress requiring some rethinking, and how soon it will attain perfection only future will tell us.”

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Annexure-1: Reporting Score of Voluntary Corporate Governance Items by Corporations during 2003-04 and 2004-05.

S. No.	Voluntary Corporate Governance Items Disclosed	2003-04	2004-05
A.	Board of Directors (7 items): Functions of the board of directors Date of appointment of directors Appointment of lead independent director Training of board members Retirement age or tenure of directors Relationship with other directors Shareholdings of the directors	3 2 2 0 2 2 1	3 2 1 1 2 2 1
B.	Meetings (4 items): Information on scheduling/selection of agenda items Duration of Board meetings Duration of gap between two meetings Procedure of Board/Committee meetings	2 1 1 3	1 2 1 2
C.	Formation of Committees (8 items): CG committee Ethics or compliance committee Nomination committee Investment committee Management committee R&D committee Risk management committee Miscellaneous	2 1 4 2 7 1 0 7	3 1 4 2 7 1 2 8
D.	Corporate Governance Initiatives (5 items): Whistle blower policy Code of conduct for directors/senior management personnel CG rating Succession planning Insider trading code	0 1 2 1 13	4 4 1 1 13
E.	Review of Committees (8 items): Compliance with Cadbury committee recommendations Compliance with Blue Ribbon committee recommendations Nomination committee report Audit committee report Investors' grievance committee report Compliance with Naresh Chandra committee Compliance with Narayana Murthy code on CG Miscellaneous	1 1 0 2 1 2 2 2	1 1 1 1 1 2 2 4
F.	Shareholders (7 items): Information on unclaimed dividends History of corporation Top 10 shareholders of corporation List of investors service centers Change in equity share capital during the year Information on Sebi Edifar filling Electronic clearing service mandate	14 1 3 1 1 17 9	15 1 3 0 2 21 9
G.	Others (1 item): Awards/Accolades for CG	0	1

(Source: Compiled from the CG Section of the Annual Reports of the Companies during 2003-04 and 2004-05.)